

Reflections on the Meaning of Contact Interruptions

A Psychosocial Essay

Abstract

This essay proposes an interpretive frame for classic “interruptions of contact” in Gestalt theory (confluence, introjection, projection, retroflexion, deflection, proflection, egotism, devaluation). I treat them not only as defensive mechanisms within the contact cycle, but also as successive stages in how a developing person learns the experience of boundaries and distance in a sufficiently non-hostile, interested environment. Two additional hypotheses structure the argument: (1) safety and development are often in counterphase in terms of energy allocation, with survival/safety taking priority when threatened; (2) early contact with a caregiving environment provides an implicit “standard” of safety that later shapes how closeness is tolerated and regulated. I suggest that the completeness or incompleteness of these processes contributes to the formation of trust, empathy, social norms, and the felt “right to choose.”

Keywords

Gestalt therapy; contact cycle; contact interruptions; boundaries; confluence; introjection; projection; retroflexion; deflection; proflection; egotism; devaluation; trust; empathy; safety vs. development; psychosocial.

1. Starting assumptions

I proceed from two assumptions.

1. **Safety and development can be in counterphase** with respect to energy consumption and the tasks an individual solves. When safety is threatened, survival mechanisms tend to monopolize energy; when safety is reliable, energy becomes available for development.
2. **Contact interruptions are archaic adaptive patterns** that can function relatively “creatively” in a sufficiently non-hostile, interested environment—an environment that, developmentally, was originally expected to be provided by the caregiving figure (first of all, the mother).

A child is an actively developing organism—physically and psychologically—and such rapid development requires a **high-safety environment** to maintain a stable energy supply for development. Phylogenetically, this is expressed in the priority of survival: first one must live, and only then one can develop. Ontogenetically, the infant initially experiences safety as delegated outward—primarily to the caregiver—through **confluence**.

2. Confluence as a baseline “standard”

I consider it imprecise to treat **confluence** as a “way of organizing contact” in the same sense as later interruptions. Rather, confluence is the infant’s initial, baseline state: physical boundaries exist, but psychological boundaries are not yet articulated as *experienced separateness*.

The memory of this state becomes an implicit **standard of “super-safety”**: the kind of safety that supports development. In adult life, people are often drawn toward this state as an image of “paradise,” “unity,” or “being held by the world.” The actions aimed at returning to it may be adaptive or maladaptive (e.g., freezing can sometimes be a more effective survival response than fight or flight).

As confluence gradually decreases, separation processes become more visible. With separation comes the need to learn boundaries—not as abstractions, but as lived experience.

3. Introjection and projection as the first boundary markers

Once psychological boundaries begin to form, the first salient contact phenomenon is **introjection**: something already formed, “dense,” and exerting “pressure” enters the child’s experience. If this “pressure” does not trigger defensive collapse—if the environment remains non-aggressive and interested—then introjection is assimilated as a **marker of form** rather than as a threat.

In this view, the **completeness of introjective processes** contributes to the formation of **trust**: the felt expectation that contact can be safe and meaningful, that what comes from the environment can be taken in without being destroyed.

A physical metaphor helps: a stone falls into water. The stone displaces water and creates ripples. After it sinks, a splash rises where it entered. In this metaphor:

- the **stone sinking** resembles **introjection** (a part of the environment “in me”);
- the **splash** resembles **projection** (a part of me “in the environment”) triggered by the introject;
- the **ripples** are the aroused energy of contacting.

The **completeness of projection**, as a counterpart to introjection, contributes to the formation of **empathy**: the capacity to perceive and understand another through analogy with oneself.

At this stage, there is not yet a firm boundary, but a **border-space** marked by two flags: an introjective marker “inside” and a projective marker “outside.” The space between them is energized. These markers become early reference points for choosing distance and regulating closeness. Their overall pattern becomes an implicit **standard of closeness**.

4. Social density and the needs of belonging and ownership

To describe further boundary formation, I introduce the notion of **social density** by analogy with physical media: piercing stone requires more energy than piercing a dandelion. Likewise, a harsh, rigid environment requires more energy to maintain contact than a gentle, responsive one.

As confluence decreases, the child develops needs that require increased energy expenditure in contact. Two of them become central:

- **Belonging:** to be “right,” appropriate, acceptable—because belonging supports safety and continued developmental energy.
- **Ownership:** a sense of power over the environment; diversification of sources of satisfaction (not relying on a single protective figure).

Many later interruptions can be understood as energy-economical ways of balancing belonging and ownership under conditions of varying social density.

5. Retroflection as a stop and a turning-back

In the border-space where trust, empathy, and reference points for closeness have begun to form, **retroflection** becomes possible.

I treat retroflection as the **stopping of outward movement** (including outward projection/impulse) when—according to accumulated reference points—the environment is experienced as too energy-costly or too risky to meet directly. If the environment remains sufficiently non-aggressive and interested, the “stop” can be assimilated as a reference point for preserving contact rather than as a signal to flee.

However, when the experience is not assimilated—when survival mechanisms monopolize energy—the “stopped” force can turn inward and become **self-directed pressure**, up to self-attack. In that sense, retroflection can contain an element of **violence toward oneself** (if violence is defined as treating a subject as an object).

The ratio of “stops that preserve contact” to “turning against oneself” becomes part of how the child forms an image of the social environment’s density, and with it, a **social self-image**. This participates in the formation of norms: what is possible, safe, permissible.

6. Deflection as a moving-aside strategy

Another physical analogy: a ball meets an obstacle.

- **Retroflection** resembles stopping or bouncing back (depending on softness/hardness).
- **Deflection** resembles a **ricochet**.

Deflection can be read as a balance between belonging and ownership: contact with the caregiver (belonging, safety) remains valuable, yet movement toward one’s interest continues (ownership). If the obstacle is soft, the trajectory shifts slightly; if hard, the deviation is larger.

In a friendly environment, deflection develops into a skill: choosing an object of interest in accordance with one’s needs, not merely in accordance with the environment’s rigidity. In an overly rigid environment, deflection yields the opposite: choice becomes constrained by fear. This is one pathway by which a social standard of the **right to choose** is either supported or undermined.

7. Proflection as empathy expressed through giving

Proflection, in a friendly environment, can be understood as an active expression of empathy: the child gives the other what the child experiences as valuable for themselves. This is not yet the mature capacity to give what is valuable *for the other as other*; rather, it emphasizes commonality (“you and I are of one blood”). It is also a form of diversifying safety: “I care for you; you might care for me.”

When such giving is directly or indirectly rejected and cannot be assimilated, fixation may emerge: the person becomes stuck in the need to complete the giving-and-being-received process. Then proflection can become compulsive and linked to restoring one’s worth rather than to contact.

8. Egotism as a revision and re-integration of values

In a friendly environment, **egotism** resembles a retroflective “reboot” of values at a developmental stage. It is a necessary period of self-focused concentration during which new self-experience (e.g., related to developmental or hormonal change) is compared with previously formed standards and reference points.

If this period is not interrupted by a shift into survival mode, its outcome is a renewed balance between changing needs/possibilities and accumulated social standards. If it is interrupted, egotism can also become obsessive due to incompleteness—similar to proflection.

9. Devaluation as a quick collapse into confluence

Devaluation (invalidation) resembles a fast way of diving into a confluence-like rest state after painful contact, especially when choice has been experienced as unsafe or humiliating.

The peak energy of contacting has already been passed; effort has been spent. If the leading meaning of this effort was protection from the pain of one’s boundaries being devalued, then “victory” over this pain may be attempted by devaluing contact itself. Yet to devalue contact one must first create it and invest energy into it. Here, the act of devaluing can become more important than the actual object—similar to how, in proflection, the act of giving can become more important than the gift.

10. The healing atmosphere

Nifont Dolgoplov once said that all a Gestalt therapist can give a client is **faith, love, and hope**. I understand the healing quality of contact as the consistent support—especially at painful moments—of an atmosphere of sincere acceptance and interest.

This is precisely the kind of non-aggressive, interested environment in which contact interruptions are not merely “interrupted,” but can be **completed** in a way that corresponds to human nature.